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From Pandemic to Apocalypse

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The present study is an urgent warning to prevent the blast of the COVID-19 pandemic to apocalypse.

There are many complex models¹ describing pandemic kinetics. In the present study we propose a minimalistic one based on chemical kinetics. If $X(t)$ is the fraction of infected people, its Markovian dynamics obeys the following evolutionary equation

$$dX / dt = \omega X(1 - X) - X / \tau \quad (1)$$

The first term on the right-hand side describes transfer of coronavirus from infected to healthy people with a characteristic frequency parameter ω . The second relaxational term is due to either recovery or death, and τ is the mean lifetime of infection. The desired solution of Eq. (1) is $X_1 = 0$ but there is another stationary solution $X_2 = 1 - 1/R$, which could be high at large reproduction number $R \equiv \omega\tau$. The deterministic Eq. (1) predicts at large time either healthy X_1 at $R \leq 1$ or pandemic X_2 at $R \geq 1$. The maximal velocity dX / dt appears at $X_2 / 2$.

A peculiarity of Eq. (1) is the chaotic behavior. Introducing the dimensionless time $T \equiv t / \tau$, being commensurable with the everyday activities, Eq. (1) changes to

$$dX / dT = RX(1 - X) - X \quad (2)$$

The discreteness of society requires use of the finite difference expression $dX / dT = X_{k+1} - X_k$ and in this case Eq. (2) reduces straightforward to the standard logistic map²

$$X_{k+1} = RX_k(1 - X_k) \quad (3)$$

Plotting the logistic map (3) shows that the pandemic solution holds up to $R = 3$, while at larger reproduction numbers the bifurcation hierarchy appears. The onset of deterministic chaos marks the beginning of apocalypses at $R > 3.5$:

In conclusion, to fight with the coronavirus epidemic the people should try to reduce the reproduction number R either by social distancing, suppressing ω , or via advance medical care, decreasing τ . In any case, a reduction of the social entropy is always helpful during crises.³

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3. R. Tsekov, How social thermodynamics could help Greece, *Research Gate* (2015) 279746509